

Longitudinal case-control study protocol for mapping caries susceptibility and could identify possible stable immunoproteomic markers in saliva

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Ethics approval

Approved by Scientific Ethics Committee of the University of Talca, protocol #23-2019 (University of Talca, 2 Norte 685, Talca, Chile, cec@utalca.cl). The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki.

Clinical study registration

<https://www.isrctn.com/ISRCTN64570618>

General study design

This unblinded longitudinal study included 46 systemically healthy adults aged between 18 and 35 years old, who attended the dental clinics of the University of Talca, Talca, Chile, from February to December 2023. Participants were invited to participate following a screening procedure conducted by a single trained researcher (J.N.B.). This screening involved radiographic (bilateral bitewing radiographs) and clinical examinations using the International Caries Detection and Assessment System (ICDAS).

Control group participants (n=25) were those without cavitated caries lesions (ICDAS 1-3) and no existing restorations. Caries group participants (n=21) had a minimum of four cavitated carious lesions coded as ICDAS 4-6.

Upon acceptance, participants signed an informed consent form and completed questionnaires to assess socioeconomic and cultural data, oral hygiene habits, and a food frequency diary. Subsequently, unstimulated and stimulated whole saliva was collected into sterile tubes on ice for 15 and 10 minutes, respectively. For stimulated collection, participants chewed paraffin film (Parafilm® M Sealing Film, Merck). Saliva collection was performed in the morning, before any meal or oral hygiene procedures, at three different time points: baseline (T0), one month (T1), and three months (T2).

After collection, saliva samples were treated with protease inhibitors, transported on ice, processed within one hour, and stored at -80 °C for subsequent analysis.

Inclusion criteria

All participants included in the study were systemically healthy adults between 18 and 35 years of age, capable of providing autonomous informed consent. They presented with normal unstimulated and stimulated salivary flow rates, good general and oral health, and the ability to comply with the experimental protocol. Furthermore, they had not used antibiotics in the three months prior to the study and were not using fixed or removable prostheses, orthodontic appliances, or other oral devices.

Exclusion criteria

Participants with systemic diseases (whether or not related to caries) that affect salivary flow (such as Sjögren's syndrome); periodontal diseases (except gingivitis); a history of antibiotic use within the last three months; regular alcohol consumption; or daily medication known to alter salivary flow, as well as smokers, were excluded from the study.

Clinical interventions

At the first clinical appointment, all participants received an oral hygiene kit containing an extra-soft toothbrush and a toothpaste with 1450 ppm of fluoride (Elmex® Sensitive Professional toothpaste, Elmex® Sensitive Professional toothbrush, Colgate Palmolive). This kit was renewed at each sampling period to ensure uniform oral hygiene conditions throughout the study. All participants received hygiene instruction adapted to individual necessities and were informed about the importance of brushing their teeth twice a day with the fluoride toothpaste.

The non-invasive/micro-invasive treatment applied to both groups included prophylaxis, supragingival scaling, topical fluoride application (Duraphat®, Colgate-Palmolive), individualized oral hygiene instruction (following international guidelines for toothbrush techniques, twice-daily brushing, and interdental cleaning), and non-cariogenic dietary counseling (reducing and controlling sugar consumption). The micro-invasive treatment consisted of the application of resin-based pit and fissure sealants (Clinpro™, 3M™, ESPE).

The invasive treatment, performed exclusively in the caries group, involved direct resin restorations (Kerr Gel Etchant 37.5% Phosphoric Acid, 3M™ Single Bond Universal Adhesive and 3M™ Filtek™ Z350 XT Universal Restorative) of cavitated lesions, tailored to individual needs. All dental treatments were carried out by a single experienced dentist (J.N.B.).

Saliva samples collection

All saliva sample collections were performed under standardized conditions, always in the morning and before food intake and oral hygiene procedures. During the collection procedures, the tubes were kept on ice. Unstimulated whole saliva was collected by passive drooling into a 50-ml Falcon tube for 15 minutes from each participant. After an interval, for stimulated saliva collection, participants were asked to chew paraffin gum (Parafilm® M Sealing Film, Merck), and saliva was then collected in a 50-ml Falcon tube for 10 minutes.

Saliva collections were performed at three distinct time points for both groups:

1. Baseline (T0):

This collection occurred after the diagnosis phase and participant allocation to either the control or caries group.

2. One month (T1):

For the caries (intervention) group, this collection followed a period of diet counseling (focused on sugar consumption), professional dental cleaning, application of resin-based pit and fissure sealants, and fluoride varnish.

For the control group, this collection similarly followed diet counseling, professional dental cleaning, application of resin-based pit and fissure sealants (if necessary), and fluoride varnish.

3. Three months (T2):

For the caries group, this collection was performed after the placement of restorations in teeth with cavitated lesions, using minimal intervention approaches.

For the control group, this collection marked the end of three months of non-invasive/micro-invasive treatments, serving as a point for comparative analysis.

After collection, saliva samples were treated with protease inhibitors (cOmplete Tablets EASYpack, Roche), transported on ice, processed within one hour, and stored at -80°C . For microbial analysis using MALDI-TOF MS, samples were analyzed individually.

Pooled samples construction

For nLC-MS/MS analysis, samples were randomly pooled to generate a total of 36 whole saliva pools. This included 18 pools for the control group (n=25 participants) and 18 pools for the caries group (n=21 participants).

Within the control group, both unstimulated and stimulated saliva samples were divided into three pools per time point (T0, T1 and T2). For each time point and saliva type, two pools comprised 8 samples, and one pool contained 9 samples.

For the caries group, unstimulated and stimulated saliva samples were similarly organized into three pools per time point (T0, T1 and T2), with each pool consistently containing 7 samples.

On average, each salivary sample contributed approximately 900 μg of protein to its respective pool. The assignment of individual participant samples to these pools was randomized using an online tool (<https://www.graphpad.com/quickcalcs/randomize1/>, accessed March 2024). This specific sample composition was maintained consistently across all time points (T0, T1, and T2).

Control group pool composition

POOL 1 USS	POOL 2 USS	POOL 3 USS
3	7	1
5	12	2
6	13	4
10	17	8
11	20	9
14	21	16
15	24	18
22	25	19
		23

POOL 1 SS	POOL 2 SS	POOL 3 SS
3	7	1
5	12	2
6	13	4
10	17	8
11	20	9
14	21	16
15	24	18
22	25	19
		23

USS refers to unstimulated saliva, and SS to stimulated saliva.

Each participant was assigned a unique number from 1 to 25.

Caries group pool composition*

POOL 1 USS	POOL 2 USS	POOL 3 USS
8	5	1
13	7	2
15	9	4
18	10	6
20	11	16
21	14	17
23	22	19

POOL 1 SS	POOL 2 SS	POOL 3 SS
8	5	1
13	7	2
15	9	4
18	10	6
20	11	16
21	14	17
23	22	19

USS refers to unstimulated saliva, and SS to stimulated saliva.

Each participant was assigned a unique number from 1 to 23.

*Participants 3 (due to medication use) and 12 (for unknown reasons) withdrew from the study, and their saliva samples were discarded, thus excluding them from the pools.